
Geotechnical Investigation and Assessment of Modern Building Foundation

*Isaac Odoi Danquah, George Amposah

*diok1982@yahoo.com, geoaomp@yahoo.com

*Water Resources Engineer, Goldrain Mountain Company Limited, Koforidua, Eastern Region, Ghana – Africa; Civil Engineer, Heerim Architect and Planners, Bunso, Eastern Region, Ghana – Africa.

ABSTRACT

The type of soil and water holding capacity is an important component and a requirement worth analyzing and assessing before a building foundation is laid. Most modern technologies applied, designed and built buildings experience structural failures due to poor geotechnical analysis, soil analysis, soil physics, nature of building, load capacity, and soils ability to support building for decades. It therefore deems fit to model, assess and evaluate the water holding capacity of soils when it comes to designs and construction of modern housing facilities. And an important aspect of the modern engineering when it comes to buildings to a given height is good geotechnical investigations and analysis. These are some of the justification for this work which is basically investigating into soil and foundation analysis towards the construction of a modern education housing facility in Ghana. From this research, it's worth noting that pile on or around bottocks or anus gives instability or unstable equilibrium position to the human foundation. While piles in geotechnical engineering and civil works gives good firm stability to the low rise and high rise building after good geotechnical engineering studies, soil physics and good civil engineering works. This research work therefore has established the need for investigation into pile from the medical background resulting in all kinds of complication and discomfort to the human existence and pile foundation resulting in stability of buildings for several decades from the perspective of the geotechnical or civil engineer. Modern high rise buildings will experience structural failures, infinitesimal slidding and distortions if proper geotechnical investigations are not done and foundations stabilized to higher degree with boulders, iron rods, high cement percentage in concretes especially in swampy areas.

Keywords: *geotechnical engineering, building, pile, load capacity, bearing, foundation, assessment, construction, education, Pile.*

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1 INTRODUCTION

For good designs and construction of modern building projects from low to high rise buildings, the survey unit needs to perform sensible geological and geotechnical survey operations on it. If the appropriate survey of the building construction project is not carried out by the use of standard operating procedures, it will directly affect the design of the building construction project and the quality of subsequent physical construction of the building. The building foundation is the critical part of any civil and geotechnical engineering works and the basic cell unit or building structure upon which all the parts of the structure/building will draw support. It therefore deem fit for a detailed geotechnical investigation of the soil upon which the foundation footing will be founded. The origin of notable engineering disasters or catastrophes involving civil structures is a repercussion from foundation distresses or problems. Significant loss of lives resulting from building collapse in sub-Saharan Africa and Ghana are as a result of bad building foundation designs, analysis and construction. In promoting the orderly construction of building project in Ghana for the 21st century and future, it is necessary to focus on the characteristics of foundation rock and soil layering. Analysis of the physical properties of foundation rock and soil, understanding the surrounding geology and topography of the construction project, and grasping the current distribution of

water and the hydrogeology in the area is very important. As an important foundation for construction engineering, the geotechnical survey is the main component of building construction and foundations for engineering projects. Hence it is very necessary to embark on various test such as soil test analysis to determine the appropriate foundation for the building based on the building height and elevation above sea level. Therefore, the *in situ* tests such as pressiometer test, plate-loading test and dilatometer test are performed to identify properties of soils as they exist naturally in the field.

Soil is a very complex engineering material from divine creation and every civil engineering project on the land is dependent on it. Its properties vary not only in vertical and horizontal directions (two dimensional analysis) but also at the location with different environmental conditions such as change in water content, temperature, presence of chemicals, moisture content etc. Therefore in designing any civil engineering structure such as building foundations, no readymade solutions are available but a need for new geotechnical investigations, assessment and research for *in situ* soil analysis. The level to which a modern building to a given height above the ground is built is based on building load bearing capacity. The types of load includes dead load, live load, wind load, snow load, seismic load etc. And in all these cases are various load stress and strain bearing forces and extensions

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against original lengths. However, non-uniformity of stress or strain distribution makes it somewhat difficult to interpret the test results from the viewpoint of identifying basic soil parameters. Thus, various kinds of sounding techniques such as the standard penetration test (SPT), cone penetration test (CPT) and vane test have been commonly used instead of routine practice to determine soil features, characteristics and load bearing ability. Because the analyzed soils are deformed largely during any penetration tests, these tests appear to reflect discreetly the deformation properties of soils undergoing large strains including failure. If an important building project is to be implemented in the area of soft soil features, more detailed information is required. In an area of higher percentage of water within the soil, there is the need for draining or abstraction of the water from the soil or using soil binding or holding materials for enforcement or enhancement of the foundation before building. Recovery of intact soil samples can be sometimes executed by means of some sophisticated techniques. Unperturbed soil samples are tested in the laboratory after sampling from the *in situ* to identify physical and mechanical characteristics of these soils before employing various foundation building techniques and strategies. The optimum role of civil engineering works is to ensure safety as well as promoting cost effective strategies during project designs and construction. The soil or ground is the ultimate foundation, as all the load generated from the construction of the building comes to ground only. If stress at any particular location in the ground exceeds the bearing

capacity of the soil then shear failure occurs and the building may collapse. The magnitude or degree of stress depends primarily on the load and type of structure constructed. For a structure of low elevation above ground level such as single story buildings foundations or low height embankments, the stress zone developed in the soil is very infinitesimal after few meters above ground level. Whereas for high rise building foundations and bridge foundation, the stress zone could be up to 20 meters or 30 meters above ground or sea level. Based on the stress zone investigations and analysis, soil samples are obtained either from trial pits or from bore holes mostly for analysis before building foundations are established.

Most of the prevalent building foundation design rules influenced by rule-of-the-thumb are often used for deciding foundation type suitable for buildings. Foundation designers uses historical geotechnical data or previous designs within the same area to decide on a suitable foundation for a proposed structure. Again, in situations where a geotechnical investigation is needed for a new project, peripheral samples acquisition and analysis is often conducted based on past experience and understanding of scenarios drawn from established projects. Additionally, the current state of practice for most construction in developing African countries involves analysis conducted on a few geotechnical parameters like consistency limits and shear strength parameters. But this approach can be improved using more detailed tests on soil physics or geotechnical investigations of the soil.

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Furthermore, an all-inclusive geotechnical investigation is required to garner full information on the soil properties, features and possible performance under structural loading bearing capacity. In addition to the standard geotechnical investigation, merging of all foundation building components and foundation load bearing capacity testing are required for the settlement and strength capacity of undisturbed sub-soil to support a best building foundation to host high rise buildings.

2 REVIEW OF GEOTECHNICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND ASSESSMENT

2.1 Modern building foundations and technology assessments review

2.1.1 Soil physics and Assessments

The soil is the most important feature worth assessing and analyzing when one is considering the building foundation for a low rise building or building to several meters above ground or sea level. Even though other features such as water, rocks layers, aquifers and if possible other natural resources exist in there, they are all found in the soil. It is worth analyzing the soil physics, testing, assessing or investigating the soil make up through geotechnical means towards obtaining an appropriate suitable foundation best fit for the building for a specific return period. Soil is the accumulation of mineral particles formed by the weathering, transportation, sedimentation and

reconstruction of rocks. The weathering process may be physical, chemical and biological. The agent of transportation can be gravity, wind, water and glaciers. The reconstruction modes include tectonics, weathering, chemistry, gravity, radiation, temperature, biological processes. (Xie et al., 2008; Yanrong, 2020). In civil engineering works, soil is a geologic material that can be broken by hand squeezing or grinding (Geotechnical Control Office, 1998; Yanrong, 2020) with modern machines to meet civil engineering purposes. The characteristics of soils mainly include physical properties (such as basic physical indicators, particle size distribution, consistency and compaction) and mechanical properties (such as compressibility and strength (Yanrong, 2020)). The soil physical and mechanical properties or characteristics after series of geologic and geotechnical investigations and research determines the appropriate and specific needed foundation for the building. And this is mostly after various test have been done on the soil. Standard Penetration Tests (SPTs) for instance was carried out at various depths in the boreholes and was generally carried out in the overburden soils, in weak rock or soil bands encountered in the rock strata during the foundation design process adopted for the Burj Dubai, the world's tallest building (Poulos et al., 2008).

Soil is a natural deposit composed of solid particles (approximately 50% of the total volume), and voids (filled with water, microorganisms and/or air) between particles. The bonding or stacking of soil particles constitutes the soil

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skeleton. The soil whose pores are completely filled with water is called saturated soil (areas within the soil worth draining for strong foundation results), and the soil whose pores are only filled with air is called dry soil (less bolstering and cementing for strong foundation)(Gong et al., 2014; Yanrong, 2020).

Soil water exerts a significant effect on the physical and mechanical properties of soil and is a direct cause of many accidents in geotechnical engineering and geological hazards (Yanrong, 2020). Soils have a three-phase composition comprising solid particles, pore water and air voids. The characteristics of soils are closely related to these three phases. A three-phase diagram is commonly used to represent the phase relationship of soil, as shown in **Figure 1**. In the figure, 'm' represents mass; 'V' represents volume; and subscripts s, w, a and v represent solids, water, air and pores, respectively. The mass of the air in soil usually has a defaults value up to 0 (Yanrong, 2020). The basic physical indicators of soil include bulk density, water content, specific gravity, void ratio, porosity, degree of saturation, dry density, saturated density and buoyant density. The density, water content and specific gravity of soil can be obtained through testing, and other indicators can be derived from the conversion of the three indicators (Yanrong, 2020). Density reflects the looseness of the soil structure and can be used to calculate self-weight stress, pressure of retaining wall and slope stability. In addition, it can be used to estimate soil bearing capacity and final settlement, and it serves as an important indicator to control the

compaction degree of the construction filling of subgrade or pavement (Yanrong, 2020).

Fig 1: Phase diagram of soil (Source: (Yanrong, 2020))

2.1.2 Rocks characteristics and Assessments

Civil engineering works in construction projects deals with rocks which are geological materials that cannot be crushed by hand squeezing or be partially scrunched. In geology, rocks pertain to lithified solid materials of igneous, sedimentary, pyroclastic or metamorphic origin (Geotechnical Control Office, 1988; Yanrong, 2020). The physical properties of rocks include porosity, density, water absorption and hydraulic properties. Among them, rock porosity exerts important influence on the mechanical properties of rocks. Void spaces in rocks include pores and micro-fissures. Pores affect water inflows and outflows in rocks. The Griffith's strength theory explains the

effects of micro-fissures on tensile strength and the brittle failure of rocks. Commonly used rock failure theories include Mohr strength theory, which mainly deals with the stress analysis of rock shear failure (Yanrong, 2020).

The ratio (in percentage) of the mass of water, m_w to the mass of the rock, m_s in the natural state is called the water content, ω . It is calculated as;

$$\omega = \frac{m_w}{m_s} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Water content is a crucial parameter for weakening rocks. Weak rocks usually contain a large quantity of clay minerals that are easily softened by water. Water content has an important dominating effect on rock strength and deformation (Shen et al., 2006; Yanrong, 2020). Rocks with great amount of water requires draining and if possible crushing before addition of hardening parameters for strong foundation establishment.

2.1.2.1 The Linear Envelope or Mohr Coulomb Criterion

The Mohr-Coulomb criterion characterizes the shear failure of rocks and is suitable for low confining pressures (Yanrong, 2020). The angle ϕ between the line and the σ axis is called the angle of internal friction, and the intercept on the τ axis is the adhesion force c and is expressed as

$$\tau = \sigma \tan \phi + c \quad (2)$$

Fig 2: Determination of material failure with Mohr envelop I – Unbroken; 2 – Critical; 3 – failed; 4 – strength envelop (Source: (Yanrong, 2020)).

If we assume that the maximum principal stress circle of a micro-body in a rock sample is tangent to the Mohr-Coulomb strength envelope, then such envelope can be ascertained from the geometric relationship shown in Fig 3,-

$$\sin \phi = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3 + 2c \cdot \cot \phi} \quad (3)$$

Thus, the conditions for determining the failure of rocks using the Mohr-Coulomb strength criterion are

$$\leq \frac{\sin \phi}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3 + 2c \cdot \cot \phi} \quad (4)$$

Or

$$\tau \geq \sigma \tan \varphi + c \quad (5)$$

From equation (3), we can obtain

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_3 \frac{1 + \sin \varphi}{1 - \cos \varphi} + \frac{2c \cdot \cos \varphi}{1 - \sin \varphi} \quad (6)$$

Under axial compression, $\sigma_3 = 0$, and from equation (3) becomes,

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{2c \cdot \cos \varphi}{1 - \sin \varphi} \quad (7)$$

Thus, the uniaxial compressive strength, $\sigma_c = \frac{2c \cdot \cos \varphi}{1 - \sin \varphi}$.

Putting $\frac{1 + \sin \varphi}{1 - \cos \varphi} = \xi$, results in equation (3) becoming;

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_3 \xi + \sigma_c \quad (8)$$

Fig 3: Mohr Coulomb Strength (Sources: (Yanrong; 2020)).

2.1.2.2 Griffith's strength theory

Rocks are not an ideal continuous medium, and they contain numerous micro-fissures. Griffith believed that when a brittle material is stressed, the end of the internal micro-fissures generates concentrated stress. When the concentrated stress exceeds the tensile strength of the material, the micro-fissures begins to expand, combine and accommodate. Finally, a macroscopic rupture appears along one or several planes or on the curved surfaces of the rock (Yanrong, 2020).

From the Griffith's theory and assuming that the fissures in a rock are flat and elliptical and that they do not affect one another, the tensile stress generated near the internal fissure tip is expressed as;

$$\sigma_b m = \sigma_y \pm (\sigma_y^2 + \tau_{xy}^2)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

Where σ_b is the maximum tangential stress around the ellipse, coefficient m is calculated as $m = b/a$ (' a ' is the major semi-axis of the ellipse, and ' b ' is the minor semi-axis), σ_y is the normal stress in the direction of vertical fissures and τ_{xy} is the shear stress in the direction parallel to the fissures. Some expressions for the strength criterion;

- a) The strength criterion can be expressed with σ_y and τ_{xy} :
When the rock is uniaxially stretched to damage, $\tau_{xy} = 0$, $\sigma_y = \sigma_t$, from equation (9). We have

$$\sigma_b m = \sigma_t + \sigma_t = 2\sigma_t \quad (10)$$

Thus, the strength criterion can be expressed as

$$2\sigma_t \leq \sigma_y \pm (\sigma_y^2 + \tau_{xy}^2)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

This formula is the Griffith strength criterion, that is, the relation between the normal stress σ_y and the shear stress τ_{xy} when the fissure starts to expand.

- b) The strength criterion can be expressed with σ_1 and σ_3 : σ_y and τ_{xy} are replaced with σ_1 and σ_3 , respectively. Then,
i) When $\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_3 \geq 0$ crack failure angle β is

$$\cos 2\beta = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2(\sigma_1 + \sigma_3)} \quad (12)$$

Then, the Griffith strength criterion can be expressed as

$$\frac{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)^2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3} \geq -8\sigma_t \quad (13)$$

- ii) When $\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_3 < 0$, crack failure angle β is $\beta = 0$

Then, the Griffith strength criterion can be expressed as;

$$|\sigma_3| \geq |\sigma_t| \quad (14)$$

According to this criterion, the following formula can be obtained under the uniaxial stress $\sigma_3 = 0$ from equation (13); we obtain

$$\sigma_1 \geq -8\sigma_t \quad (15)$$

The Griffith strength criterion is proposed for brittle materials such as glass and steel, and it is therefore only suitable for studying the destruction of brittle rocks. For general rock materials, the Mohr-Coulomb strength criterion is much more applicable than the Griffith counterpart (Yanrong, 2020).

2.1.3 Foundations Load bearing Capacity

Load bearing capacity and ability is the most important factor worth considering in every building foundation. Low lying building foundation have a low load bearing capacity comparably to a ten story building or high rise building. The level to which a modern building to a given height above the ground is built is based on building load bearing capacity. The types of load includes dead load, live load, wind load, snow load seismic etc. Even in situation where building foundation is close to heavy earth moving machines, waves generated by constant

movement of such machines around the building foundation have resultant future foundation and structural failures. And in all these cases are various load stress and strain bearing forces and extensions against original lengths. The building load can be carried on spread or strip footings, on a raft or mat foundations, or on piles. If the soil is weak and for the given load there is a risk of shear failure below the foundation, then the loads must be reduced, carried to a stronger underlining layer by piles (Mohsenian et al., 2011). In Cases where there is no alternative for changes in site or soil, then various techniques such as draining of water from aquifers, compactment, use of boulders, iron rods of varied sizes, increasing cement to sand ratio or only cement in the water etc are used for the enforcement. Alternatively, the applied load can be reduced utilizing a floating foundation, in which a total or partial superstructure load can be compensated by excavating the soil. The technique of reducing the total and differential settlement of a foundation by decreasing the net applied load by excavation is called floatation (Mohsenian et al., 2011). Bearing capacity of a foundation is the maximum load that can be applied on a foundation before structural failure or uncontrolled deformation occurs after reaching the elastic limit of the foundation. In the case where the maximum load (Force) is directly proportional to the extension, one should expect the foundation to hold the building whether low lying building or high rise building for some return period. But the moment the maximum load (force) exceeds the elastic limit of the foundation, then there will be structural failure, tearing,

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distortion or deformation. Structural failure is also subject to seismic conditions or eventualities. All these analysis are subject to modern buildings by civil engineers.

2.1.3.1 Modulus of Deformation

Similar to the elastic modulus of an ideal elastomer, the deformation modulus E_o of soil is the ratio of stress to strain under unconfined conditions. The value reflects the ability of the soil to resist elastoplastic deformation caused by external forces. This ratio can be determined by a loading test or pressure meter test and is often used to represent instantaneous settlement (Yanrong, 2020). The relationship between soil deformation modulus and compressive modulus can be expressed as

$$E_o = E_s \left(1 - \frac{2\mu^2}{1 - \mu} \right) \quad (16)$$

The Poisson's ratio μ of soil is usually less than or equal to 0.5; therefore, the deformation modulus of soil is always smaller than the compression modulus. The parameters obtained from the soil compression curve can be used to calculate the settlement s of the soil (assuming that the soil is compressed under confined conditions) (Yanrong, 2020); that is,

$$s = \frac{-\Delta e}{1 + e_1} H \quad (17)$$

$$s = \frac{a}{1 + e_1} \Delta p H = m_v \Delta p H = \frac{1}{E_s} \Delta p H \quad (18)$$

where Δp is the additional stress loaded above the soil (kPa) and H is the height of the soil before compression.

By the conditions of loading, the compressive deformation of soil usually includes two parts: elastic deformation and plastic deformation. After the load is removed, only the plastic deformation is retained (Figure 4a & 4b). In the compression curve, the ring formed by the unloading and recompression process is called a hysteresis loop. In the e - $\lg p$ diagram, the area of the hysteresis loop is small. In practice, the hysteresis loop is often treated as a straight line. The slope of the line is called the rebound index C_s and can be calculated from the expression

$$C_s = \frac{e_1 - e_2}{\lg p_2 - \lg p_1} = - \frac{\Delta e}{\lg \left(\frac{p_1 + \Delta p}{p_1} \right)} \quad (19)$$

where C_s is the rebound index; p_1 , p_2 are the compressive stress at the two ends of the hysteresis loop; and e_1 , e_2 are respectively the void ratios corresponding to p_1 , p_2 .

Fig 4a: Curve of soil rebound against recompression (Source: (Yanrong, 2020; Wu, 1982)).

The recompression curve of the soil indicates that the stress history of the soil exerts a significant effect on its compressibility and that the compressibility is significantly reduced when it is pressed again. The maximum stress experienced by soil is called preconsolidation stress p_c . The ratio of the preconsolidation stress p_c to the effective stress p_o of soil is called the overconsolidation ratio OCR . OCR is also an important indicator for soil classification; $OCR > 1$ is overconsolidated soil, $OCR = 1$ is normally consolidated soil and $OCR < 1$ is underconsolidated soil (Yanrong, 2020).

Fig 4b: Curve of soil rebound against recompression 1 (Source: (Yanrong, 2020; Wu, 1982)).

2.2 GEOTECHNICAL TESTING TYPES AND METHODS

2.2.1 Pile Load Testing

A pile is a long cylinder made up of a strong material such as concrete. Piles are pushed into the ground to act as steady support for structures built on top of them. Piles transfers the loads from structures to hard strata, rocks or soils with high load bearing capacity. Piles are long pillars that extend downwards into the ground to keep the building above ground level stable. Pile load testing is the process of evaluating the

performance and characteristics of piles. Pile testing methods includes Maintained Load Test, Constant Rate of Penetration Test, Bi-directional Load Cell, Rapid Load Test, Static Pile Load Testing (axial and lateral), Dynamic Load Test and Pile integrity Testing (PIT).

2.2.1.1 Static Vertical Load Testing

The static vertical load testing is the most basic testing type and involves the application of vertical load directly to the pile head, usually through a series of increments. Test procedures have been developed and specified by various codes including ASTM D1143 (Poulos, 2015). This test is regarded as the most definitive test and the one against which other types of test are matched. It is a best fit test for pile load testing because of its ability to simulate the way in which structural load is applied to the pile. The usual fundamental data from such a test is the load – settlement relationship from which the load capacity and pile head stiffness can be interpreted. Caution is needed in the interpretation as the measured pile settlement may be influenced by interaction between the pile and reaction system (Poulos, 2015).

2.2.1.2 Static Lateral Load Testing

A lot of lateral load test exist but the most common and adaptable is the jacking of one pile against one or more other piles and for example is the ASTM standard D3966. In the case of the static vertical load test, there are negative effects

especially in the case of two piles jacked against other piles. Because the direction of loading of each pile is different, the interaction between the piles will tend to cause a reduced pile head deflection and as a repercussion, the measured lateral stiffness of the pile will be greater than the true value (Poulos, 2015).

2.2.1.3 Dynamic Load Test

The test procedure and routine is accepted solely for quality control and design confirmation purposes. Despite its widespread use, the dynamic pile load test has a number of potential limitations including the load – settlement behaviour estimated from the test is usually not unique, but is a best – fit estimate. Two measurements (strain and acceleration vrs time) are taken and interpretation for the complete distribution of resistance along the pile as well as the load – settlement behaviour is done (Poulos, 2015). Under normal design load levels, the amount of time – dependency (from both consolidation and creep) is relatively small as most of the settlement arises from shear deformation at or near the pile – soil interface. Therefore the dynamic load test may give a reasonable assessment of the pile head stiffness at the design load. Dynamic load testing is generally not suitable for heavy loaded foundations such as in supporting tall buildings since insufficient energy can be imparted to the pile to fully mobilize its load bearing capacity. But the test may provide acceptable

means of obtaining the head stiffness of a single pile (Poulos, 2015).

2.2.1.4 Bi – directional Test

The Bi – directional Test was developed by Osterberg (1989) with a similar one developed in Japan (Fujioka et. al., 1994) which is been increasingly used worldwide. A special cell is cast in or near the pile base, and pressure applied. Jacking of the base is done downwards while the shaft provides reaction. Until the element with the smaller capacity reaches its ultimate resistance, the test continues (Poulos, 2015).

Fig 5: Pile factor in foundation stabilization

2.2.2 Pressuremeter Testing

Pressuremeter testing can be used to estimate both strength and stiffness properties of the ground before any building foundation is done. Interpretation of test result is discussed by Briaud (1992), Mair and Wood (1987). The stiffness values relevant to foundation design are generally the values obtained from the reload loop (Poulos, 2015).

2.2.3 Resonant Column Testing

This type of test is usually used for laboratory measurement of low – strain (ratio of extension to original length) properties of the soil. It subjects solids or hollow cylindrical specimen to torsional or axial loading by an electromagnetic loading system. This is usually harmonic loads for which frequency and amplitude can be controlled. This test measures the small strain shear modulus and damping ratio of a soil or rock sample. It again looks at the variation in modulus and damping ratio with increasing shear strain level. Such results are valuable for carrying out dynamic response analysis of the foundation system (Poulos, 2015).

3 GEOTECHNICAL OUTPUT FROM FIELD INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Geotechnical Investigations and Assessment

Geotechnical investigation, soil and rock assessment is very important when analyzing for the foundations of low rise and high rise buildings. Structural failure and distortion is likely to

happen if the various loads to impact the building either positively or negatively are not well calculated and factored into the designing of the foundation, its building and the resultant building. Loads such as live load, dead load, wind load, seismic load, snow load (not in the case of Ghana) need to be well calculated before building the foundation of the high rise building. The various characteristics, nature and attributes of the soil and rocks also ought to be critically analyzed before selecting the appropriated foundation. For instance, the foundation for a high rise building in a swampy or water logged area will not be the same for a dry clay soil area. The climatic condition of the zone or area for the foundation or construction also need to be assessed. Since there is the possibility of some areas receiving more precipitation more than others although within the same zone. With this assertion, precipitation within a catchment leading to infiltration, soil saturation and soil holding capacity will be different. It is established in geotechnical investigation and foundation analysis that once the drilling hit a rock underground, then foundation can be established there. That is ok but further analysis need to be done as hitting that rock can be on a confined aquifer. And if abstraction from that aquifer is done continuously mostly from the use of bore hole water, that confined aquifer may result in future structural failure if a break in the aquifer occurs. This can be seen in a case where the pile and resultant foundation is established there.

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Pile is a medical condition full of pain, torture, distortion, discomfort and instability when looking at human mindset and foundation when siting among a group for instance. This same pile is seen in geotechnical engineering or civil works when establishing strong building foundations. In building high rise building for longer return periods, it's one of the adapted and acceptable methods for strong building foundation. But why the contradiction from medical field to the engineering field. This is worth investigation and further probing. All should have result in strong foundation establishment for support above ground level or point of stability or equilibrium.

3.2 Building heights against Foundation Assessment

History of both Africa and western world record of very low lying building height in Africa comparable to the western world. Massive buildings in Ghana were built to a few meters above ground level and this is seen in the major regional capitals and is mostly state institutions. These building structures have existed over the years but justified by the quality of building and strong foundations. Modern Ghana is experiencing both good civil engineering works while bad engineering also prevails resulting in structural failures and building collapse in some cases. Bad feasibility studies, the use of old building designs and not using the state – of – the – art method, use of bad geotechnical engineering procedures and not developing and building foundations based on current state of land characteristics and topography. All these results in structural

failure or building foundations fracture. Poulos (2016) lists a number of factors that may influence the type of building foundation to support tall buildings. These includes;

- The site location and the structure to be constructed.
- The various loads under considerations and their distributions.
- Land and ground conditions during geotechnical investigations.
- Durability requirements.
- Accessibility to land and ground by earth moving machines.
- Heavy machines used for drilling and installations may even alter the building foundation after geotechnical investigations approval.

With some of these factors, building a high – rise – building is worth serious geotechnical studies, analysis before foundations are laid as Ghana seek to move in the direction of Dubai's, UK, China, USA etc. Poulos explains tall buildings like Burj Khalifa in Dubai which is 828m and the Kingdom Tower of Jeddah in Saudi Arabia which is currently under construction and will be 1000m above the ground are worth analyzing by engineers and countries. Since most are presenting difficulties to geotechnical and structural engineers. It is therefore very necessary for proper geotechnical and civil engineering investigations and assessment of location and site, be well certain and assured of

findings before constructing buildings of high rise on well designed and constructed building foundations.

3.3 Building Foundations and Human Gold Production

3.3.1 Building Foundation analysis

The building of basics or fundamentals forms the integral part of every endeavor or adventure and so is the foundation of a building. Either building to a few meters above ground level or high rise building, well designed and constructed foundation is worth in supporting all loads to be generated by the building. The foundation component to support all parts of the building requires feasibility studies, geotechnical engineering, the study of the physics of the rocks and soils, aquifers, movement of water underground, soil layers and structures and so on. Based on the nature of soil, whether dry or swampy soil area, water logged, 90% water coverage or in the sea gives the geotechnical engineer the choice to study the zone of construction through all kinds of studies and design the appropriate foundation. Without a good building foundation, all building structures will not be justified for a given return period for modern buildings in Ghana. The ratio of force to area resulting in the tensile stress on a building ought to be in balance. If all the loads generated towards the building given the total pressure to be exerted on the foundation is not balanced with the area of foundation, one should expect structural failure. Some of the loads includes wind load, dead loads, live loads, seismic loads, snow load (not applicable in

Ghana) and so forth. All these loads are analyzed and factored into determining the total force to be exerted on the land (foundation) by the building. For structural failure or distortion to be experienced, the Hooke's law needs to be disobeyed. The moment the elastic limit of the building foundation is exceeded, then there will be complete deformation, distortion or breaking hence total crushing of the building or structural failure. With these assertion in mind, it is very important to ensure strong enforcement of building foundations especially in the case of building high rise building or building to several meters above sea level or ground.

3.3.2 Building the strong foundation for quality Human gold production

With this research work which deals with geotechnical investigation and assessment of building foundations built for academic purpose, so is the need to look at the strong foundations component that needs to be built when dealing with human gold production in Ghana. The human gold product looks at how one identifies academia or learning as the ultimate path and root towards greatness or enrichment in life. And hence justifies it by climbing the academic ladder from kindergarten to doctor of philosophy (PHD) level and beyond. In this case, one goes through a series or all kinds of learning, courses and programs after a well-defined choice of program, profession or career. The student or individual goes through all the pressure, the hustles, struggles and mid night burning of

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candles for several years. This is what one goes through and in doing so, builds a very strong foundation (comparable to a strong building foundation for high rise buildings) in a chosen field or path through academia. All in the name of being refined into pure gold medal, bar or refined individual or personality for greater works or to impact generations in the future. This is where real gold products in the form of graduates are obtained in various fields to help build the nation and world. And the study area for this research work is justified in doing same for now and future generations. With this engineers, agriculturists, scientists, artist, business men and women and other professionals will be trained, refined and obtained as pure gold bars products to serve mankind and future generations. The pure gold products has the potential of serving nation or being shipped to other countries to help build a beautiful world for all. This will help address all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) as there will be eradication of poverty, hunger, promote good health and well-being, quality education (quality human gold production), gender equality, provision of water and electricity. Other SDG's goals to be attained will include creation of job opportunities, infrastructure development, address climate changes, improvement in production of goods and services, obtain a peaceful world, promote life below water and on land and finally, ensure stakeholder participation and partnership among all the goals. Human gold production is of utmost importance to the well – being and development of country and world. It is therefore very necessary for a balance between real gold production obtained underneath the ground

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and human gold produced through various studies and schools of thought.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Strong foundation building and stabilization is very important both in the direction of building low rise buildings or high rise buildings. Various techniques are employed by geotechnical engineers and civil engineers in establishing a zone or area for feasibility studies, assessment and building of strong foundation for a selected type of building. The load bearing capacity of the building is dependent on the various loads such as wind load, dead load, live load seismic load, snow load etc and this is obtained after various assessment and investigation. The best foundation stabilization technique such as the pile method can be employed for a strong foundation underground to support and receive all loads from the building for a given return period.

Comparably to strong foundation in building for a given return period, is also the need for a strong foundation in the lives of every individual when it comes to the process towards attaining real human gold to support country and world. Real human gold is produced through various means but in terms of academia is through schooling in build structures. And such built civil engineering structures should have strong foundation to avoid structural failures, deformity, collapse as it meet it purpose of containing students to be trained and developed into real gold bars (experts in various fields) for the world. Pile

is an interesting foundation technique when comparison is done in the direction of medical field and in civil or geotechnical engineering field. That is as stability is generated from strong foundation though pile in civil works; instability, discomfort, pain, agony and torture is exhibited by pile (*Kooko*) from medical background or practitioners. Therefore does this expression ring any bell to civil or geotechnical engineers and medical practitioners, '*installing into or around your anus or buttocks as pile (Kooko) for a firm strong foundation stabilization as pile*'. This is worth noting and further probing.

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